

CHILDREN & YOUTH PERSPECTIVES CONFERENCE
THEORY, RESEARCH AND PRACTICE IN EUROPEAN CONTEXT
PRAGUE 14TH - 15TH SEPTEMBER 2023

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

This conference is part of the project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 101027291 for project ENCOUNTER: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships.

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Conference is co-funded in partnership:

Funded by
the European Union

H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 Project no. 101027291 Encounter: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships
Faculty of Humanities, Charles University in Prague, the Czech Republic

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1. KEYNOTE SPEAKERS ABSTRACTS

1.1. KEYNOTE 1: What can Childhood Studies add to Policy and Practice?

Kay Tisdall, The University of Edinburgh, Scotland

How we conceptualise children and childhood matters. It impacts what we study, how we study it and our conclusions; it also permeates how we form and deliver policy and practice. This presentation will review the legacy of childhood studies' foundational ideas -- that childhood is socially constructed and that children are social actors in their own right -- and subsequent debates around agency, materiality and intergenerational relations. It will consider how such ideas are not only of conceptual interest but have very practical implications, using examples in such areas as children's activism, children's rights and children's wellbeing. The presentation will end by exploring current challenges and opportunities to further develop childhood studies, from decolonization to childism, to consider the future for childhood studies and its implications for policy and practice.

Short bio

Prof. Kay Tisdall is Professor of Childhood Policy at the University of Edinburgh.

She is part of the Childhood and Youth Studies at Moray House School of Education and Sport. Her policy, academic and teaching work is centred around childhood studies and children's human rights. She undertakes collaborative research with children, young people and adults on such as areas as children affected by domestic abuse, family law, inclusive pedagogy for young children, young people's mental health, and children's participation and activism. She is involved in a number of partnership projects, with teams in countries ranging from Brazil, Canada, Eswatini, India, Palestine, and South Africa, funded by such organisations as the British Academy, the Canadian Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council, the European Commission, Global Challenges Research Fund, and UK Research and Innovations.

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1.2. **KEYNOTE 2: Theorizing Global Childhoods: Philosophies, Theories, and Practice.**

Marek Tesar, The University of Auckland, New Zealand

This keynote presentation explores the concept of global childhoods and investigates the various philosophies, theories, pedagogies, and methodologies that influence this field. It delves into both global and local discourses surrounding childhood experiences and critically examines the contemporary challenges and opportunities faced by scholars and practitioners engaged in the study of global childhoods. By analyzing the complex interplay between global and local factors, this presentation integrates diverse perspectives and approaches within this area of research, including the relations between Global North and Global South scholarship. The keynote presentation builds on both traditional childhood studies scholarship and posthuman perspectives, and merges scholarship and activism. Its aim is to stimulate dialogue and reflection on the evolving nature of childhoods in a globalized world, encouraging scholars to consider the implications of their work and the potential for positive change in shaping the lives of children worldwide.

Short bio

Prof. Marek Tesar is Head of School of Learning Development and Professional Practice, and the Associate Dean International at the Faculty of Education and Social Work, University of Auckland.

He is also the director of Centre for Global Childhoods. His award-winning scholarship is focused on early childhood education in both New Zealand as well as in cross-country contexts. His academic work and consultancy focuses on educational policy, philosophy, pedagogy, methodology and curriculum, and draws on his background as a qualified teacher. Currently, Marek serves as a leader of two leading learned societies in his fields; he chairs the Steering Committee of the Reconceptualizing Early Childhood Education (RECE), and is elected President of Philosophy of Education Society of Australasia (PESA). Marek's scholarship and activism merges theoretical work with a practical focus on the everyday lives of children and their childhoods in Aotearoa New Zealand and overseas. Since 2018, Marek has been leading a team of New Zealand early childhood experts to deliver a curriculum framework, and teaching and parenting programmes in China. In 2020, Marek was appointed as a Research Fellow at SEAMEO to provide expertise on future research and development initiatives and programmes, and enhance cooperation in education, science and culture in Southeast Asia.

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1.3. **KEYNOTE 3: Children's Studies – training the next generation of practitioners.**

Michal Molcho, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

The perceptions of children and childhood has changed dramatically over the course of history. Overtime, childhood was seen as a biological stage of development; a psychological state of development; a legal status; and these views are reflected in the way children are seen and treated today. Indeed, the new Sociology of Childhood has moved from viewing the child as 'becoming' to the child as 'being', but in order for such concepts to actually influence practice, we need to provide practitioners with the knowledge and skills that are required to implement a truly child-centred care. In this key note presentation, I will present how the BA in Children's Studies aims to develop T-shaped practitioners that are best equipped to work with children and adolescents.

Short bio

Prof. Michal Molcho, Head of the School of Education and founder of the Department of Children's Studies @University of Galway, Ireland is a world-renowned expert in the sociology of children and youths. She founded the Department of Children's Studies at NUI Galway in line with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child: the only such department in Europe with a child-centred, multidisciplinary perspective. Currently, she serves as a Head of the School of Education @University of Galway.

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1.4. **KEYNOTE 4: Spoiled weirdos and puppets of the Left? Cultural specifics of and intersectional perspectives to the discursive construction of youth civic activism in the Czech online media.**

Lenka Vochocová, Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University

The presentation will summarise the results of a three-year project focusing on public representations of politically active youth in the Czech online mediated public sphere and the youth perceptions and interpretations of their public representations. It will reveal online media's tendency to provide youth activists with selective attention, often making some of their identity characteristics hyper-visible and leading to fragmented media coverage of their activities. It will further document that online civic discussants employ a variety of discursive strategies to exclude politically active youth from political participation and deny them political roles and show similarities between the exclusion of youth and the historical exclusion of women and other vulnerable groups. It will specifically focus on the intersection of age, as the dominant factor in play, with other arbitrary factors, such as gender, sexuality, socio-economic status, (dis)ability, or lifestyle, and interpret these exclusionary strategies from a socio-cultural and historical perspective.

Short bio

Dr. Lenka Vochocová is a lecturer and researcher at the Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Department of Media Studies, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University in Prague, where she graduated in journalism and media studies. Her research interests cover the fields of political economy of communication, gender media studies and public sphere theories. She currently studies political participation in the social media environment with a special focus on gender aspects of online deliberation, polarisation of the online public sphere and discursive exclusion of vulnerable actors, including youth. She has been a member of the Gender expert chamber of the Czech Republic since 2015. She regularly participates as a principal investigator and member of research teams of both domestic (Czech Science Foundation) and international projects (COST Action).

2. PRESENTATION ABSTRACTS

2.1. CHILD-CENTERED THEORY, CONCEPTS AND RESEARCH METHODS

2.1.1. Leila Angod: Conceptualizing “voice” in school – based youth participatory action research: Constraints and new possibilities in anti-racism research.

A key dilemma of school-based youth participatory action research (yPAR) is that this methodology often constrains youth voice in ways that run counter to its promise of social transformation. This occurs through the controlling role of schools, adult-youth hierarchies, and limited possibilities for action through what Rubin, Ayala & Zaal (2017) name the “schoolification” (p. 135) of yPAR into a series of assignments that are “bounded empowerment” (Keddie, 2021, p. 382), depoliticized, (Brion-Meisels & Alter, 2018; Call-Cummings, Sheanain & Buttimer, 2022), and beholden to schools’ agendas and efforts to control public perception (Ozer & Douglas, 2013; Stoudt, 2009). In this presentation I draw from focus groups and participant observation from a school-based, anti-racism yPAR study that I co-led at a Toronto school to elucidate methodological constraints and possibilities for youth voice. I employ Black and women of colour feminist theoretical, ethical, and political lenses (Angod, forthcoming; Collins, 2000; Collins & Bilge, 2016; Crenshaw, 1991; Lorde, 1984; Razack, 1998) to demonstrate how youth voice is shaped by the cultures of school and of yPAR projects in ways that not only work against the social justice commitment of the project, but that put the youth researchers at risk of increased racism and gender-based violence by their peers (Angod, forthcoming). I then show how I applied these findings to design my current school-based yPAR project with an Ontario school board, using arts-based methods that I call “the multiverse as method,” to explore the relationship between institutional and personal voices together with youth researchers. This presentation contributes to critical youth studies by deepening notions of and facilitator approaches to the construction of youth voice in school-based yPAR.

Keywords

yPAR, schools, anti-racism, methodology, voice

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Short bio

Dr. Leila Angod (she/her) is an Assistant Professor in Childhood and Youth Studies at the Institute of Interdisciplinary Studies, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario in Canada. Dr. Angod's research mobilizes anti-racist, critical feminist, and decolonial theories and methodologies to examine how schooling discourses, policies, and practices invite young people to live racial orders, and how youth research can create the conditions to contest and subvert these racial orders.

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2.1.2. Letizia Luini: Photo-production during research processes with children: free expression and participatory possibilities through photovoice.

Children's lives, what children are and should be, are often reconstructed through adult interpretations (Mayall, 1994), making children objects of research processes (Alderson, 2005): this reflects childhood images that considers them as incomplete subjects subordinate to adults (James, Prout, 1990). Recently, we are gradually observing a paradigm shift that is having implications in research through the implementation of methods capable of enhancing children's voice, supporting their expressive and participatory potential: this represents a change in children's position, understood as competent agents who have something to say. In this perspective, visual participatory methods value children's unique ways of seeing reality (Burke, 2005) through child-friendly language (Shaw, 2021) and empowerment processes. The paper reflects around photo-production during an exploratory research conducted in two Milan preschools, using photovoice methodology (Wang, Burris, 1997): previous empirical researches highlighted that adults play a crucial role during the research process due to the potential power dynamics (Devine, 2013; Morrow, 2003) and the risk of more or less consciously influencing children's responses. So, compared to traditional research processes with interviews, these dynamics are subverted with photovoice: field collected observations show that the concrete action of pictures' creation permits child involvement as active participants (Samanova *et al.*, 2022), allowing them to express themselves beyond external constraints (Butschi, Hedderich, 2021) through the self-production of the favorite snapshots. This action is less affected by adult influence, which enables personal activation through concrete production of subjective meanings. In conclusion, the immediacy, the freedom and the possibility for creative actions during the photo-production in photovoice, allows preschoolers to express themselves freely and more independently than during interviews, thus supporting agency and self-expression in an engaging process.

Keywords

photo-production, photovoice, agency, personal expression, participation

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Short bio

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2.1.3. Maria Manuel Vieira & Lia Pappámikail: Gaining access and cooperation: Some methodological challenges in research with adolescents.

This presentation addresses a fundamental aspect of research with children and adolescents: can the access to research subjects guarantee their cooperation in the research process? As we know, scientific research is itself a social process. The process of gaining access to a target population is a crucial stage of the entire research process. Considered a potential "problem" in any sociological research, it takes on particular contours in the case of studies with adolescents (1). Like any other research subject, the adolescent presents him/herself to the researcher as an individual skilled in the production of a reflective discourse on his/her life worlds and the meanings awarded to them. However, the specificity of their social and legal status - minors and economically dependents (2) - poses particular challenges and obligations. Securing consent for researcher access to adolescents given by legal gatekeepers (3) is one such challenge, following strong ethical constraints and procedures imposed by the new General Regulation of Data Protection (GDPR) on research with humans (4). Due to the specificity of this age period in which peers play a decisive role as an instance of identity validation and existential shelter of adolescents (5), a relative closure to the adult world (and to adults themselves) may also occur, with significant implications for research (6). This presentation intends to highlight specificities of the research involving adolescents. It is based on two qualitative research studies with young people (7), both involving the same approach - youth-centred - and adopting the same technique - the in-depth individual interview - but whose divergent outcomes allow us to raise a number of methodological questions. The results suggest: a) the importance of gaining the trust of these participants, which implies time in accessing the field and in some cases the existence of strategic mediating actors. b) The interference that the social properties of the interlocutors (interviewer - interviewee) may exert on the research process. c) The relevance of the information produced is found not only in the data which we are able to collect, but also in the data which we are unable to access.

Keywords

adolescents, methodological reflexivity, gaining access, sociology

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Short bios

Dr. Maria Manuel Vieira is Principal Investigator @Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal. She is a sociologist and works as a senior researcher at the Social Sciences Institute (UL). Coordinator of the Permanent Observatory of Youth. Former Vice-President of the Portuguese Sociological Association. Her research interests and publications focus on sociology, education, and youth. Current projects on NEET youth and youth sexual education.

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2.1.4. **Ruth Barnes: Exploring children's wellbeing and the concept of 'generagency' in sport: a youth sports case study.**

While children's participation in competitive sport is often considered beneficial to wellbeing, there is increasing concern over risks including non-accidental harms, injury and excessive exertion. Still, children continue to participate, with the support, encouragement and consent of their parents and others. Sports-related research has delved into children's participation and wellbeing in sport (E.g. Fortier et al., 2020; Lang, 2022), while childhood studies has explored concepts of agency in varying contexts using multiple tools (E.g. Esser et al., 2016). However, research has yet to examine how children's agency in sport could be connected to or interact with wellbeing and harm. This presentation reports on research that addresses this gap. The field research, completed in Spring 2023, centres on a single case study of a youth rugby club in England with embedded units of analysis in the form of child-parent-coach triads. Research methods include analysis of club and governing body documents, observation of training sessions, group discussions and semi-structured interviews with children aged 14-17 years old, and semi-structured interviews with parents, coaches and coaching officials. The presentation will discuss findings relating to children's views and understandings of agency and wellbeing, locating this within participants' constructions of a 'rugby family'. It reflects on the opportunities offered by Leonard's (2016) 'generagency' lens to explore children's agency within this 'family' construction; a 'family' that is grappling with physical and mental health wellbeing risks both inside and outside of the sport. The research thus presents, for the first time, an insight into children's, parents' and coaches views and understandings of children's agency and how these support or otherwise impact children's experiences of wellbeing in sport.

Keywords

wellbeing, generagency, family, children's sport

References:

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2.1.5. Natascia Micheli: Theological intelligence and learning in adolescents.

The young Western generations, rich in cultural, ethnic, and religious differences, question the *humanities* and especially pedagogy within a theological and spiritual future. The age of sad passions, theorized by Benasayag and Schmit (2013), describes a youth universe marked by the ideology of crisis, severe fatigue, psychic suffering, confusion, addiction, and fear. Riccardo Massa, announcing the sunset of education (Massa, 2000), uses the image of the sun and its journey to the *educational darkness*, aware that the direction of the sun turns to the hope of the dawn (Martini, 2008). This paper, reports an educational experience from transdisciplinary practice intended as a scientific, artistic, and theological approach toward understanding the world of youth. Through *theological exercises* with adolescents aged 16 to 22, an educational experience of immersion in an ancient village and its nature in northern Italy is described. Starting with an in-depth analysis of some images from one of the best-known medieval bestiaries of the 12th century, an adolescents' own ability perform theological intelligence through artistic research and theater emerges is explored in four elemental moments: analysis of images from the Bestiary; analysis and recitation of *Psalms 8*; creation and decoration of the *Mask*; and improvisational theatre on the theme of the *Name (Genesis, 2:19-20)*. Data analysis can represent an opportunity for pedagogy to listen to urgent demands from the contemporary youth world. The discussion on the desacralization and secularization of the West, suddenly seems to veer towards the opposite direction starting from a theological problem posed by adolescents: *the need to learn God*.

Keywords

pedagogy, theology, theater, adolescents, learning

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2.2. CHILDREN, UN CRC, SOCIAL DISADVANTAGES, INSTITUTIONS, AND SERVICE

2.2.1. Sheila Garrity, Monika Haid & Aidan Harte: Spaces and Traces: Young children's meaning making through digital methodologies in a time of global pandemic.

'Spaces and Traces' involved young children, early childhood educators, and students in the University of Sanctuary, participating as co-researchers, exploring a university campus as a community space. The project embodied a pedagogy of citizenship and presence, viewing the campus from young children's perspectives. Our presentation will touch on themes of equality, diversity, and inclusion, through the project fieldwork, its outcomes, and future possibilities. Notions of belonging and identity are central to Aistear, Ireland's Early Childhood Curriculum Framework which situates the very young child as a rights holder, a citizen with agency and autonomy. Developing a sense of citizenship begins early, as children participate in their local communities, experiencing their voices being heard, and their opinions shaping outcomes. This project connected to theoretical understandings of place and space, belonging and identity, relationships and meaning making. Our methodology was based on the Mosaic Approach. Aligning with Aistear, reflecting a sociological and rights-based construction of the child, informed by Halpenny's work and the concept of pedagogy as inquiry. We will demonstrate how the spirit of the Mosaic Approach as a democratic, participatory, non-hierarchical methodology was respected, and extended. Familiar methods of photo-voice, mapping, and child-led tours, pedagogical observations, and documentation were adapted to virtual contexts during the Covid 19 pandemic. We argue that the relationship formation, a sense of belonging and meaningful connections to a 'place', by young children, can be facilitated through digital methodologies, intentional foundational work, and collaborative partnerships.

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**2.2.2. Pierangelo Barone, Camilla Barbanti, Veronica Berni & Monica Facciocchi:
Speaking up through research, taking the floor in society: a participatory research
study on the impact of the theatre laboratory at the "Cesare Beccaria" youth
detention center in Milan.**

Drawing on the results of a qualitative, participatory research study on the impact of theatre laboratory at 'C. Beccaria' juvenile prison in Milan, the paper aims to explore the perceptions and give voice to the views of young inmates on the value and impact of the theatre workshop experience. Through phenomenological interviews, ethnographic observations and certain methodological attentions, the research gathered participants' views in terms of their experiences, needs, desires and aspirations. In particular, the researchers investigate how young inmates signify and live educational experiences in the prison context and in relation to the detention pathway in which they are placed. The voices collected are not only fundamental as testimonies of the youths' point of view, but also become a valuable element for adults, primarily the professionals involved, as they enable them to reflect critically and from a pedagogical perspective on the prison re-educational mandate. Work remains namely to be done regarding the re-educational task that characterises the enforcement of a sentence in juvenile prison, particularly with respect to the task of reintegration, which has declined as social inclusion and active citizenship education. Hence the contribution, through the lab participants' voices, reflects on the educational model implicit in theatre practices with specific regards to the peculiar mode of participation in social life that it allows and to the agency that this experience gives back to the young inmates. Finally, we will show how theatre in prison turns out to be capable - as an "embodied" practice which allows through a performance to take the floor in the public space - of changing the participants and of transforming not just their positioning in the social structure but partially the social structure of the prison itself. Adolescents, and adolescent inmates, thanks to the medium of theatre and the magic circle of its play space, return to being protagonist social actors since they find a way and have space for a new presence and visibility/voice in the public scene of the city. The theatre lab makes it feasible for them to enact new ways of taking part in the world.

Keywords

theatre, young inmates, enaction, embodiment, participation

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2.2.3. Karin Osvaldsson Cromdal, Jacob Kromdal & Daniel Persson-Thunqvist: Agency and ambiguity in young children's emergency calls.

In interaction between citizens and public organizations, age precedes other categories. Calls to the emergency services (112-calls) may be one of the few exceptions, where it can be argued that the nature and emergency of the call takes priority (Cromdal, et al., 2012). Nevertheless, when issues concerning the authenticity of the call arise, the caller's age may be *made* relevant as a source of trouble for the operator's decision. In a collection of calls to the Swedish emergency services initiated by children some calls raised concerns for the operators regarding the veracity and actionability of the reported incident. A majority of these calls appear to be phoned in by young callers. Typically, such calls were handled with a measure of skepticism as potentially false, but would not be discarded as pranks unless the operators were convinced of that being the case. It will be demonstrated that operators work is geared towards trying to establish the relevant details of the incident so as to assess the authenticity of the information. This can be a complicated endeavor though, as the child may be pursuing a different agenda. The analysis demonstrates both the sequential unfolding of these interactions alongside the different categories made relevant by the parties. These categorisations may prove decisive for taking action on the presumed emergency. In effect, the study points to the artfulness in the young callers' framing of ambiguity as well as the operators work to disambiguate vital details of the reported events. This is done through a series of procedures such as asking questions with candidate answers, asking for other sources of information, postponing problematic exchanges and even going on record with questioning the child's narrative or pledging for the truth. The analysis makes a case for very young children's competence in keeping a conversation going while pursuing an interactional project even though this project may not coincide with the aims of the emergency operators.

Keywords

agency, ambiguity, interaction, young children

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2.2.4. Laura Migliorini, Martina Olcese & Paola Cardinali: Children Wellbeing and material deprivation: research data and practical implications.

In recent years, interest in the study of children's subjective well-being has increased, but knowledge about the factors that contribute to it, as well as its implications, is still limited. More specifically, recent research has found relationships between children's perceived well-being and the possession of material goods, in particular the increase in material deprivation corresponds to a decrease in subjective well-being. However, the issue is complex and not all research aimed at confirming this association has reached the same conclusion.

The present study is part of an international research on children's subjective well-being (ISCWeB), which aims to fill an important gap in international knowledge about children's lives. The research is based on the child-centered perspective, which aims to recognize, take into account and strengthen children's voice and active agency by viewing children as active and relevant social actors with their experiences and perspectives.

The aim of the study was to determine the relationship between well-being and material deprivation among 3000 school-age children (8-12 years) living in Italy. The research was carried out in Italy in primary and secondary schools, drawn through stratified sampling.

In the present work, the following scales were considered: Overall Life Satisfaction; Russell's Core Affect, Personal Well-being Index; Student's life satisfaction scale, N-Deprivation. The main results are presented and data on deprivation will be explored in more detail considering what material things have the greatest impact on children's well-being. Theoretical and practical implications will be discussed.

Keywords

Subjective well-being, material deprivation, life satisfaction, material goods, , International Survey of Children Well-Being

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2.2.5. **A matter „of course“: Children’s rights in schools and educational self-concept in children’s rights education. The example of the Child Rights (Respecting) Schools initiatives in Austria**

Children’s rights at school? Of course they apply there and should be taught – who would seriously be against children's rights? There is also hard any objection to the fact that educational professionals should know children's rights. Not only to teach them as part of their educational mandate, but also to ensure that they are respected. And yet the Austrian school system can be described as anything but child-friendly. A central problem are the school curricula and pedagogical trainings, which do not or only insufficiently, not systematically consider children’s rights (Schrittesser/Kobesova 2019). There are already initiatives, such as the Child Rights Schools or Child Rights Respecting Schools (UNICEF 2014), that aim to bring about a systemic change in this regard. The inherently structural problem is being adressed with an internationally approved program concept. The input of such programs deals with the possibilities of integrating the program into the current legal framework in the country concerned and assumes, there are ways to close legal loopholes for, at and with schools. Can it work, or do schools risk crossing borders in their educational mandate? Or does this encourage new pedagogical hypocrisies, the denial of the interests of the child, when teaching can come close to the ideal of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, but can never achieve it to perfection? The lecture explores the possibilities and limits of pedagogical action orientation on children's rights in a heavily regulated environment by analysis of educational concepts and legal school requirements (esp. curriculum for primary schools, SchUG, SchOG). Finally, it reflects on the potential of school framework development through children's rights.

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Short bio

Mag.^a phil. Zuzana Kobesova in her work, educational theory, curricula analysis and the pedagogical practice of action (teaching, social pedagogy, elementary pedagogy) enter into a lively discourse, thus opening up the possibilities for social innovation through children's rights. In this translational approach, she trains future school teachers, but also kindergarten teachers, educators and child care workers in Austria and Germany. In parallel, she publishes on children's rights in the field of curriculum studies.

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2.3. CHILDREN PLAY AND IMAGINATION

2.3.1. John Potter & Michelle Cannon: Partnership and empowerment in research practice with children.

This paper draws on qualitative and ethnographic research focusing on children's play in two consecutive projects, funded by the UK-based Economic and Social Research Council: 1) *Playing the Archive* (2017-2019) centered on archives of historic school playground activities and links that could be made between these and contemporary play practices, with children as co-producers of the research and 2) *The Play Observatory* (2020-2022) which took place online during the pandemic, and set out to explore how some young people responded to the crisis through creative, playful and agentive media-making. Children and their parents and carers were invited to make contributions to a national database of stories, texts and artefacts associated with their play during the pandemic. As part of the research design, both projects sought the collaboration of young participants as co-researchers, with responsibilities for data collection/dissemination, peer-interviewing and/or making media, all of direct relevance to the research outputs. Methodology was constructed in ways that maximised the participation of children and young people as participants and as co-researchers. For example, by creating an accessible survey design, a flexible approach to multimodal contributions, an online youth film-making workshop, and the documenting of children's voices and perspectives in participant family interviews. These inclusive approaches resulted in a rich collection of national and international data from diverse communities. We believe the empowerment associated with self-determined research practice and creative production help us to understand the lived experience of young people, inclusive of their ideas, concerns and the cultural pursuits that make sense of their lives. Drawing on methods and data from both projects we derive deeper understandings of children's perspectives that are so often regarded as ephemeral. We propose that our methods could serve as blueprints for holistic and agentive approaches to researching in partnership with children, as authentic collaborators and co-agents in research practice.

Keywords

empowerment, participatory research practice, co-production, creative media

Short bios

Prof. John Potter is Professor of Media in Education at University College London Institute of Education. Director of ReMap and Associate Director (Media) Knowledge Lab. His research, teaching and publications are in: new literacies, media education, play on and offscreen, curation and agency in social media, and the changing nature of teaching and learning in the context of digital media.

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2.3.2. Beata Patuszyńska: Empowering children through co-creation. Case study of writing a book with and for children about their first steps into urban independence.

Children are practically absent in Polish urban planning processes. That results in a vicious circle: unfriendly urban space discourages children from using it independently and as a result adults do not see the need to make the space child-friendly, because children are not present there. The exclusion has been reinforced even further with pandemic restrictions and a perception of children as a pandemic threat. I will present what I learnt from the project I have undertaken during the pandemic – co-writing with children a book concerning first steps into urban independence. The project was aimed at empowering children in finding their voice when it comes to deciding about urban space and was a continuation of my research into children’s urban independence. The project assumed participation of children at every level of creation. Children were: (1) models: the narrator is an 8-year-old boy, who is getting ready for urban independence. He shares his experience as well as experience of his school friends and his 11-year-old sister, who already travels on her own; (2) teachers: the book is based on authentic children’s stories and experience as well as findings of research I carried with children earlier. The material was extended by conclusions collected during the pandemic; (3) reviewers: prototype chapters were reviewed with children during workshop in school. In my presentation I will discuss (1) advantages of creating together with children; (2) research results: perception of urban space by children age 8-9, when they start their independent travels in the city, barriers and pleasures of independent urban travels, as well as influence of the pandemic on children’s feelings and behavior in urban space; (3) my conclusions of how to work with children in participatory processes.

Keywords

children, urban space, co-creation, participation

Short bio

Beata Patuszyńska is a researcher and an advocate for children’s rights in a city. Having a professional background in the property sector and being a mother, she investigates children’s experience in urban environment. In her work she focuses on children age 7-10, who start their urban independence. She shares her findings via conferences presentations, writing and educating. She is the author of a blog cityforchildren.pl and a children’s book “Urban Games”. A leader in Placemaking Europe Network and a member of KIDS working group. She is based in Warsaw, Poland.

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2.3.3. Anezka Kuzmicová & Karolina Simková: Children thinking about facts via nonfiction book design.

In traditional research and educational settings, children are assessed as readers based on their liking and/or comprehension of a relatively narrow range of reading materials that belong in the fiction genre and that have been preselected for them by adults. Children who prefer nonfiction to fiction tend to be stereotypically seen as geeks and associated with lower imaginative and socio-emotional inclinations while reading (Mackey, 2019; Scholes, 2020). We have conducted a child-centred creative interview study in which diverse children in the Czech Republic (N = 20, age 9-11) reflected on the world of facts as a springboard for imaginative activity, on a par with the world of fiction. First, children made collages of their individual real-world interests and then used flashcards to reflect on different types of imaginative activity (e.g., playing, making, reading, watching, chatting, thinking) through which they nurture these interests. Second, children engaged in the design of an imaginary nonfiction book, a process that involved laying out a double-page spread, leafing through actual nonfiction books, and sorting picture cards representing different text and image elements. In our paper, we will present the interview “toolkit” (Kuzmičová et al., 2022) followed by two contrasting case studies of children (age 10-11) who both manifested particularly strong affection for facts; these two children’s inner worlds defied, each in a different way, the stereotypical disconnect between facts/nonfiction and imaginative/social engagement. We will discuss the possible uses of our toolkit in educational settings and the implications of our findings for practice.

Keywords

participatory design, child-centred research, literacy, nonfiction, imagining

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Short bio

Dr. Anezka Kuzmicova (Ph.D. Stockholm, 2013) studies reading in various forms, focusing on how children become engaged in stories and how they relate to nonfiction contents in print and other media. She runs the Integrating Text & Literacy group at Charles University, bringing together researchers from across the humanities and social sciences.

Karolina Simkova is a Ph.D. Candidate at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University. As of 2020, she conducts research into media literacy and media education mainly in the Czech context. She focuses on the perspectives of teachers on digital media and its use in the classroom.

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2.3.4. **Grace Spencer & Jill Thomson: Problematizing empowerment: unpacking young African migrants' concepts of power and empowerment – implications for youth agency in the European context.**

Concepts of empowerment pervade popular discourses on young people and the term is often applied uncritically as a means to leverage young people's perspectives on matters that affect their lives and support their agency. Despite such focus, little critical work exists that unpacks the meanings, relevance and utility of the term for young people, or indeed considers the possible unintended consequences of the concept. Drawing on a qualitative study with young African migrants in Ghana, we explore young people's own understandings of power and empowerment and consider the relevance of such conceptions for enhancing young lives and agency. Specifically, we tease out the broader implications for young people living in the European context. Data were generated from focus groups, dyads and interviews with 59 young migrants aged 15-24 years and analysed using Spencer's (2014) conceptual framework for empowerment. Our findings highlight how dominant socio-cultural norms shape young people's possibilities for agency and social change – raising critical questions about the relevance of empowerment to the lives of (marginalised) youth in the Global South and who live and work in ever-changing and vulnerable contexts. Our analysis advances the conceptual elaboration of empowerment as it relates (or not) to the lives of young migrants, with important implications for broader discourses that privilege notions of youth empowerment in the European context, and without due regard to young people's own perspectives and circumstances. We consider how varying socio-cultural contexts and dominant norms about childhood/adulthood within those contexts shape the possibilities for the conceptual advancement of empowerment and how the term may be best utilised to support positive youth futures in Europe.

Keywords

empowerment, power, migration, agency, youth

References:

Spencer (2014). Young people and health: towards a new conceptual framework for understanding empowerment. *Health*, 18(1), 3-22.

Short bio

Dr Grace Spencer is Associate Professor in Young People, Health and Social Equity. Faculty of Health, Education, Medicine and Social Care, Anglia Ruskin University, UK. Her international programme of research focuses on concepts of empowerment, power and risk as they relate to young lives and health. Drawing on ethnographic and participatory forms of research, she has a particular interest in exploring social change, migration and vulnerabilities with young people.

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2.3.5. Jacob Cromdal, Sally Wiggins & Annerose Willemsen: Food for fantasy: Sharing imaginary worlds during preschool meals.

Play has long been understood as an important pedagogical practice, particularly in ECEC settings, yet playing with food during mealtimes has been overlooked or undervalued. The apparent dichotomy between rule-following and playfulness at mealtimes has led to a paucity of research on food play. Adopting an ethnomethodological approach that seeks to describe social activities from the participants' own perspectives, this paper examines instances in which young children initiate pretend play with their food during mealtimes. Data is taken from a large corpus of video-recorded lunches in Swedish preschools and a collection of pretend play sequences were analysed using multimodal conversation analysis. The results show that pretend play is multimodally achieved, directed first to teachers, often involves other children, and enables the multiactivity of playing and eating. Moreover, the analysis illustrates how food is handled to allow for the initiation of pretence scenarios and for sharing those imaginary worlds with other participants at the table, especially the teachers. Accepting the invitation, teacher's responses were fitted to narratively build on and contribute to the imaginary events, while at the same time orienting towards the progression of the meal. The findings are discussed in terms of the pedagogical work of teachers, whose efforts to ratify the children's perspectives and trigger their imagination co-exist with the institutional demands of eating lunch together.

Keywords

child-teacher interaction, preschool mealtimes, pretend play

Short bio

Prof. Jakob Cromdal is Professor in educational practice in the Department of Behavioural Sciences and Learning, Linköping University, Sweden. He specializes in postcognitive approaches to social interaction – mainly ethnomethodology, conversation analysis, discursive psychology, and membership categorization analysis. His most recent projects focus on two settings for socialization in preschool: mealtimes and group outings passing through traffic environments. Email:

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2.3.6. Denisa Kollarova: Playground potentials: Tools of imagination.

Over the past sixty years public playgrounds, in cities internationally, went through a large shift in terms of their design aesthetics and concepts. This resulted in a global trend of playground companies becoming a widespread phenomenon. The design of these catalogue playgrounds, on one hand infantilize adults worlds; on the other, their safety fencing and colour palette character sets them apart from it. What have we gained, and what lost, when shifting from artistic approach into an industry of playgrounds? I propose to think alongside Friedrich Froebel's pedagogy, and the playground forms designed by architect Aldo van Eyck. Thinking with Froebel can expand the process of play as produced through encounters with forms and the environment where play creates an awareness of the self and the outside world, and the interactions between the two. His pedagogy emphasises activity as the means for learning and becoming aware. Van Eyck's playgrounds captured my attention primarily because their design contrasts with contemporary catalogue design. Van Eyck's play elements - 'Tools of Imagination', as he referred to them, were meant to support children's creativity as they were designed for multiplicity of meanings. Playgrounds create a core vocabulary of children's play experience in urban space. We should therefore critically review how, and by who, these environments are designed today. Over the last ten years, through my design practice, and specifically, the *Seventeen Playground* project, I have produced a body of fieldwork and empirical materials. In Amsterdam, I recognized two types of playgrounds for their different design, materiality and the children's interactions they invited. There were the colorful and theme-oriented catalogue playgrounds which contrasted with those designed with a sensitivity to the surrounding built environment. The latter, designed by the renowned Dutch architect Aldo van Eyck, were the core of the large Amsterdam Playground Project (1947-1978) which brought to the city over 700 playgrounds. I am proposing to expand on the 'Tools of Imagination' by introducing Froebel's Gifts as possible tools and as a methodology of further experiments. I approach this research using my background as a socially engaged, interdisciplinary designer with research through design.

Keywords

playground, design, Froebel, Aldo van Eyck, architecture

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Short bio

Dr. Denisa Kollarova holds PhD in Education and Design and lectures and research @Manchester Metropolitan University in UK. Denisa combines her expertise in graphic design, architecture

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research and playground design to create interdisciplinary projects. She is a founder of the *Seventeen Playgrounds* project, studying playground situations as cultural resources around the world.

Currently pursuing her PhD at MMU in Manchester, while also teaching graphic design at FaVU, Brno, previously based in Dessau, Berlin (2017-2019), and in Amsterdam (2009-2017).

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2.4. CHILDREN AND SPACE

2.4.1. **Minkyung, Kwon: Teenage girls navigating and challenging the contradictory construction of a 'girl-child': a theoretical contribution of 'childism'.**

Drawing on one-year ethnographic research with a teenage girl feminist activist group in South Korea, I aim to suggest the potential contribution of childism to understanding girl activists' navigation of the contradictory discourses constructing their sense of selves as a girl-child in this presentation. Childism, as conceptualised by John Wall (2022), provides a critical lens for deconstructing the adultist social and political foundations upon which children's lives are envisioned, and for reconstructing more age-inclusive scholarly and social imaginations through difference-responsive approach. Childism further enriches the contributions made by the childhood studies perspective, as it not only aims to understand children's experiences from their own viewpoint but also engages in critiquing and transforming the social understandings that have been predominantly shaped by adults. Using an interdisciplinary approach that combines childism and feminism, I present four cases where girl activists' critical questions against the contradictory constructions of a girl-child were observed: (1) 'make-up', representing body shame on females and regulation of teenage schoolgirl behaviour; (2) 'absence of sex spaces', representing ambivalent role as a sexually objectified female and a non-sexual child; (3) 'teenage feminist practice in schools', representing anti-feminism and conditional feminism in schools; (4) 'school uniforms as a pornographic metaphor', representing sexual fetishisation of childhood innocence. These four cases suggest that identifying adultist as well as sexist discourses contributes to gaining a richer understanding of the complex and often contradictory construction of a girl and a child, and girl activists' active challenges for reconstructing their sense of selves as a girl-child.

Keywords

childism, teenage girls, girl-child

References

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Short bio

Minkyung Kwon is PhD candidate in Childhood and Youth Studies Research Group in Moray House School of Education and Sport, University of Edinburgh, Scotland, UK, studying teenage girl feminists' activism upon the SchoolMeToo movement changing the school culture that silences sexual harassment against girls. Interested in learning about critical perspectives questioning children and young people's marginalisation and exclusion in different contexts, and experiencing different research methods to actively listen to their voices.

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2.4.2. Helena Szewiola: Children in public space.

Children are often ignored in public discussion and decision making, this is also true for the area of spatial planning. Aside from playgrounds, children are not being thought of as fully functional inhabitants of cities. Due to that misconception, their needs are not being met in public spaces. The presented research focuses on the area around schools, covering the journey a child takes every morning and afternoon. The basis of the research are the results of a survey of over 700 children about their relationship to public space. Building upon that, a series of workshops with children has been conducted to focus more thoroughly on specific spaces around the school area, where children spend their time. This should allow to redefine spaces, based on the perception and use of children and establish a network of child-used public spaces. The gathered knowledge will be used for further research into the needs of children in regard to the city and can be a baseline for better inclusion.

Short bio

Helena Szewiola is PhD Candidate, Faculty of Architecture, Silesian University of Technology, Poland. Graduated of Architecture, currently teaching urban planning and working in an architectural studio in Silesia. Her research focuses of the topic of children in public space; a minority that has been widely ignores in spatial planning. Organizer of many city oriented event in Silesia, including A<FESTIVAL, the workshop series URBAN KIDS and the design marathon A<24.

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2.4.3. Molly Brooks: Urban livability and well-being: An evidence based approach to young peoples participation in research and creating change.

This paper sets out the rationale, methods and findings from my PhD thesis exploring the impact of urban livability on young people's wellbeing. Poor transportation, fewer job opportunities, abandoned physical spaces, lack of healthy food choices, and a lack of green space are all features of what makes a community livable, and their absence affects every part of one's life, including health and wellbeing (Badland and Pearce, 2019). This led me to develop the research question: How do young people's interaction with environments, (economic, physical, social) shape their wellbeing in Drumchapel, Glasgow, UK? The field of youth development and wellbeing in the UK emphasizes a participatory approach to achieving change (Hagen, 2021). The UN New Urban Development Action Plan (United Nations, 2016) alongside the UN Sustainable Goals (United Nations, 2015) shows the shifting focus of mental health and livable cities as a priority to the UN. The methods included ethnographic observation and arts based participatory activities with 20 young people aged 12- 18, as well as collaborative data analysis. The three themes that emerged included that young people's experiences of urban livability are impacted through the formation of their identity through discriminatory experiences, environmental justice, which, in turns affects their social mobility and life outcomes. This contributes to the field of international development, and childhood rights by amplifying the perspectives of the young people through evidence based practice and continues to further exemplify the need to have children and young people as co- researchers (Tisdall, 2016). The young people are currently using PAR (Lowenson et al., 2014) methods to disseminate our findings to stakeholders in their area to create change.

Keywords

children and young people participation, health inequalities, urban livability, well-being, children's perspectives

References

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Short bio

Molly Brooks is PhD Candidate in International Development @University of Edinburgh, UK where she teaches in the faculties of Social Work and Sustainable Development. She also contributes to ongoing research in Childhood studies in partnership with the ICCRP and the Children's Parliament of Scotland.

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2.4.4. Alexandra König, Jessica Schwittek & Katarzyna Jendrzey: The Child as an Agent in Transnational Families - Methodological and Theoretical Considerations Using the Example of a Polish-German Research Project.

Temporary labour migration is both easy and widespread between EU member states. These migrations create not only work connections, but also transnational families. The migration of mothers is often scandalized in public discourse, and their children are stigmatized as Euro-orphans. The children are thus depicted as purely passive victims of their parents' interests. In the public as well as in the academic debate about transnational families, children themselves rarely get a chance to have their say. In our current Polish-German research project "Growing up in transnational families. Children's perspectives on good childhood" we focused on the perspective of children and ask how they perceive and evaluate such family arrangements. The data is based on group discussions with 12- to 14-year-olds in Poland. In this presentation, we will present key findings indicating that children are concerned not only about the absence of a parent but also about a) the lack of involvement in the decision-making process, b) the alternative care arrangement determined by the parents, and c) the shifting of generationally assigned tasks. It becomes evident how strongly the children demand space for co-determination and thus (also) identify different problems than in the public (adult) discourse. In addition to (potentially) problematic aspects of transnational family settings, children also discuss them as a place for generating transnational capital. We argue for a stronger consideration of these active contributions of children to processes of European citizenship and identity formation.

Keywords

transnational families, transnational childhood, participatory research, methodological reflections, research ethics

Short bios

Prof. Alexandra König, PhD. is a Full Professor of Research on Socialization at the Faculty of Educational Sciences at the University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany. In her work, Alexandra focuses on childhood, youth and family in different societies and constellations. Of special interest to her work are variations and negotiations of the generational order and normative patterns of childhood and intergenerational solidarity.

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Dr. Jessica Schwittek is a Post-doctoral researcher in the work group of Socialization Research at the Faculty of Educational Sciences at the University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany. In her work, Jessica focuses on childhood, youth and family in different societies and in contexts of migration and transnationality. Of special interest to her work are variations and negotiations of the generational order and normative patterns of childhood and intergenerational solidarity.

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Katarzyna Jendrzey is a PhD Candidate and researcher in the work group of Socialization Research at the Faculty of Educational Sciences at the University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany. In her work, Katarzyna focuses on childhood, family and migration. Of special interest to her doctoral thesis are transnational family arrangements and media representations of transnational families.

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2.4.5. **Sonja Arndt, Kylie Smith & Nicola Yelland: Conceptualising ‘the migrant child’:
Feminist, poststructural and posthuman speculations.**

This conceptual paper responds to contemporary concerns with research involving migrant children and childhoods in an Australian context. With migrations occurring around the world and researchers and teachers’ attention being drawn to enhance the cultural wellbeing, identity and belonging of young children, we ask the question: who is ‘the migrant child’? In our response to this question, we disrupt expectations of simplistic, homogeneous views of children of migrant families or backgrounds, including confronting such notions as vulnerability, neediness and deficit. Using a feminist, post-structural and posthuman theoretical framing we draw on Julia Kristeva, Gilles Deleuze and Felix Guattari and Rosi Braidotti to argue for elevating the complexity of conceptions of migrant children’s powerful and agentic engagements with and contributions to their own lives. Potential ways in which ‘the migrant child’ is implicated by diverse social, environmental and political factors underlie the many ways in which children might exercise their autonomy and participation. In Australia contemporary migration remains clouded by such policies as the only relatively recently overturned ‘White Australia’ policy and so-called ‘boat turnbacks’, whilst, and especially in post-Covid times, Australian society simultaneously depends on migrant workers in many fields. It openly celebrates what is superficially seen as ‘successful’ multiculturalism. These multiple perspectives offer a deeply concerning social and policy environment for researchers and educationalists. It is in this context that we raise questions and speculate towards potential conceptualisations of ‘the migrant child’ which recognise, rather than negate, the powers and insights arising from the child’s experiential, relational and deeply entangled onto-epistemological perspective/s.

Keywords

migrant child, poststructuralism, feminist posthumanism, children’s agency, global childhoods

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Short bios

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2.5. CHILDREN AND MEDIA

2.5.1. **Ashley Woodfall: Who Do You Want to Be? Participatory Creative Method in a Study into Children's Media and Aspirations.**

In this presentation I will be sharing insight into an exploratory child-centred participatory approach adopted during a small-scale study into children's media and children's aspirations. With the aim being to look into any differences between the aspirations of those children that engage with higher levels of US produced media content and those that engage with more UK produced media content – which in this setting can also be framed as differences between those that engaged with more or less public service media content. Research was conducted with 16 ten and eleven year-old children. Avoiding an 'effects' bound approach common to studies that look at possible media-facing correlation/causality, the study focussed instead on children's lived media experience, and recognised the agency and competence of children to talk for themselves - as both participants and researchers – whilst also acknowledging approaches that value participant creativity. The tasks were co-designed with child participant-researchers, who helped shape the fieldwork interactions, and acted as research facilitators on the day – with the actual research interactions becoming those between peers, rather than adult to child. The participant-researchers were introduced to a range of research tools that they could adopt to address a research question (e.g. interview), but also offered the freedom to design and adopt their own research tool. The participant-researchers were drawn towards tools that might be said to sit, partly, under a 'creative research method' approach – and selected a questionnaire, role play and drawing a picture, and then self-designed a listening task. The child participants were then guided by the participant-researchers through the role play task (of them being 'heroes'), responding to audio recordings (of the same words said in an US and UK accent) and the drawing (of themselves, anywhere in the world, doing whatever they wanted). With these tasks stimulating children's 'aspirational' responses. The study, in its admittedly limited way, identified that what a child watches might be seen to impact on their aspirations. The presentation will ultimately reflect on the value and viability of working with children in creative and participatory research settings.

Keywords

youth aspirations, participatory research, research co-design, arts-based research methods, children, youth and media

Short bio

Dr Ashley Woodfall is a Senior Principal Academic, Bournemouth University, UK. Ashley worked in children's television for many years before joining the teaching and research community at Bournemouth University (BU). He is Editor of the *Media Education Research Journal* (MERJ) and Co-Editor of the *Children's Media Yearbook*. He is on the Executive Committee of the UK's Children's Media Foundation (CMF) and Co-convenor of its Academic Advisory Board.

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2.5.2. Lydie Karnikova & Karolina Simkova: Young activists' perspectives on how society views their civic engagement in the online space.

This paper aims to contribute to the growing body of research focused on the ever-evolving forms of political participation (Theocharis & Van Deth 2018) in relation to youth (Banaji & Mejias 2020, Pickard 2019) and digital media (Tilleczek & Campbell 2019). It addresses the numerous contradictions embedded in the issue of youth activism in the digital age while acknowledging the crucial role of media in the social construction and negotiation of children and childhood (Trültzsch-Wijnen & Supa 2020). Drawing on the results of a Q research conducted in the Czech Republic with activists under the age of 18, the paper explores the varied perspectives of civically engaged youth concerning digital media and the online space. It illustrates how young people perceive both the potential and the downsides. Based on the data retrieved from a media content analysis of the media representations of civically engaged youth under eighteen, a set of 39 statements about the engaged youth was compiled for use in a subsequent Q research (Brown 2008). Within the ongoing online data collection to be finalized by April 2023, a total of thirty under 18 years old activists have been interviewed via Zoom, sorting the statements and discussing the participants' decisions in post-sorting interviews. Through this, we engage the youth in an active dialogue about the social construction of "a young activist" resulting from the analysis of adult-governed online content. We invite them to compare their media image with their own lived experience and to share their perspectives on civic engagement and digital media. A full by-person factor analysis of the sortings, combined with a reflective thematic analysis of the post-sorting interviews, will reveal the engaged youth's distinct subjective experiences of online spaces and their personal perspectives on the role of digital media in their civic engagement.

Keywords

youth, civic engagement, activism, digital media, Q methodology

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3. SYMPOSIUM

3.1. "It's so good just to be!" pedagogical practice - respecting children's rights.

This symposium brings together Early Childhood academics from The Open University, UK and Debrecen University, Hungary focusing upon children's rights and how they are understood in Hungarian pedagogic practice. Central to each of the papers is the voice of the child and the relationship between children and pedagogues/other adults so that children's voices are heard, listened to and engaged with. The papers focus on child-centred, evidence-based evaluation and practice. They draw on different elements of a two-year research project: the findings from analysing data generated by children focusing on their preferences and views; the arts-based representation of the project findings with the involvement of the Vojtina Puppet Theatre and the way in which recognising children's rights and empowerment are significant in understanding children's embodied and lived experiences.

Sándor Pálfi: Listening and hearing children's voices through rights based pedagogic practice.

One of the general principles of the UNCRC that plays a fundamental role in realising rights for all children is the right to be heard (Article 12). This paper focuses on children's voice and how Article 12 is realised in pedagogic practice as children's views and preferences are listened and responded to through play activities. 15 Kindergartens each typically accommodating 150 children between the ages of 3-6 years old across Hungary participated in the research. Pedagogues from each Kindergarten selected a play-based activity from a toolkit devised between the researchers and pedagogues in the first phase of the study. These activities focused on children's participation, eliciting their views and opinions on their lived experiences. Children generated data through their play which was video recorded, photographed or observed by pedagogues and some activities generated artefacts. Pedagogues talked to them about what they had made and what was important to them. Pedagogues were also asked to reflect on the power relationships between themselves and children in enabling Article 12, as they engaged with children's perspectives through listening and interpreting children's embodied meaning making. 7 dominant themes emerged through reflexive thematic analysis: Ownership, Voice, Space and Place, Adult Dominance, Children's Autonomy, Significant People, Essentials for Life. These themes were checked with the children through child-centred participatory workshops and involved artists from the Puppet Theatre Company who created a puppet show reflecting the findings, that brought to life children's conversations and messages that children thought were important. This paper offers a situated and nuanced understanding of how the participatory nature of research supports a process of interpreting children's voices and raises awareness of the issues around the realisation of children's rights expressed in Article 12.

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Keywords

UNCRC Article 12, thematic analysis, children's voice

Short bio

Prof. Sándor Pálfi is a professor and Head of the Department of Early Childhood at the University of Debrecen, Hungary, where he teaches the principles of pedagogy of play. His research interests are children's rights and voices, the project approach, child-centred pedagogies and the adults' role in supporting children's play.

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Eleonora Teszenyi: Representing and interpreting children's voice through an arts-based platform.

This paper focuses on the process of engaging young children in the process of representing their thoughts and feelings through an arts-based outlet, a puppet show. The interpretations of children's perspectives are grounded in sociocultural theory where children's play is infused with cultural meaning. A significant element to the research was understanding children's voice in multiple ways and through data generation it was clear that drama, imagination and role play was a significant part of children's play and connection with each other. Harnessing children's embodied expressions and communication to explore their meaning making was central to representing the findings with a collaborative partner, Vojtina Puppet Theatre, who provided bridging to an arts-based platform to visualise children's views as interpreted by adults. To mitigate against the power imbalance between adults and children, the scriptwriter adopted a verbatim documentary approach and through multiple visits to kindergartens it was checked with children that their voice and lived experiences were authentically reflected in the creative process. The puppet show reflected ideas children played out that bore significance in their daily lives and highlighted children's rights conceptualised as the things most important to children. The relationship between research and arts-based interpretation of findings contributed to shared knowledge and understanding. The paper highlights the significance of disciplines working together through the notion of slow pedagogy to develop relationships as well as respecting children's rights at the critical juncture of two different set of ideologies and value bases. The full show premieres on International Children's Rights day in November 2023.

Keywords

arts-based interpretive paradigm, visual representation, embodied expression, slow pedagogy

Short bio

Eleonora is a Lecturer at The Open University, UK with substantial experience in early childhood practice as a teacher and advisor. Her research focuses on children's rights and voices, parent and

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practitioner partnerships and early childhood pedagogies, in particular, pedagogic practice in multi-age environments.

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Natalie Canning: Acknowledging children's rights as a process to empowerment.

Children experience moments of empowerment in play situations as a result of social interactions and experiences with other children. They demonstrate their empowerment through negotiating play relationships with peers, expressing their choices, curiosity, creativity and making meaning from different situations. This paper examines the challenges of pedagogues recognising children's empowerment. The data from the research focused on children's rights is also analysed through an empowerment framework where children's actions and reactions from play based on a toolkit of activities focusing on eliciting children's views about their rights is examined from an empowerment perspective. The ethnographic nature of this research draws on video data featuring children's play and focus groups with pedagogues reflecting on how children conveyed their thoughts and feelings about their rights through their play and interactions with their peers. The toolkit of activities serves as a cultural platform for children to explore their lived experiences from their family and community and for those experiences to be examined through a rights-based and empowerment lens. The empowerment framework used as an analytical and reflective tool supports the significance of listening to children, creating shared understanding of how children's participation, voice and ownership supports not only a process of empowerment but reflects children's rights. Consequently, the research asks pedagogues to focus on developing practice that recognises the significance of a process of empowerment and that forefronts play as a means to a right's respecting basis for practice, learning and development.

Keywords

empowerment, ethnography, participation, voice, ownership

Short bio

Natalie is a Senior Lecturer in Early Childhood and a Co-Director of the Children's Research Centre at the Open University, UK. Her research centres on children's empowerment in play, outdoor play and learning, creative spaces and professional development. She is a co-convenor of the European Early Childhood Outdoor play group.

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4. WORKSHOP

4.1. **Agnieszka Krzyżak-Pitura, Helena Szewiola, Beata Patuszyńska & Gooitske Zijlstra: "Towards Child-Friendly Cities: The Importance of Inclusive Urban Space Design and its Impact on Children's Well-being".**

The workshop is run by Placemaking Europe Kids Working Group, which operates within the framework of Placemaking Europe network. It will present the importance of including children's rights and perspective in designing urban space, different levels (authorities, society, families) of inclusion, as well as how child friendly cities influence children's mental and physical well-being. Based on the Polish background we'll show how doing the absolute minimum during the planning process of public space influences child's discrimination. We will also highlight the differences between participation of adults and children in the planning process. Although the spatial planning processes and procedures are unique to Poland, the initiatives to involve children can be uniformly and widely implemented everywhere. We will show that involving a broad spectrum of social groups into spatial planning procedures is important and would benefit all sides. A child-friendly space is a space where children's rights and developmental needs of safety and play are observed. The level of it's friendliness has a huge impact on children's independence in the urban space as well as the way children interact with it. That, in turn, influences their mobility, the way they spend their free time and in consequence, their health. Urban areas that are heavily reliant on car transportation can lead to children being exposed to polluted air, which constitutes a violation of fundamental human and child rights as enshrined in the Polish constitution and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UN CRC). The pervasive presence of cars in cities also deprives children of opportunities to engage in recreational activities, interact with peers, and relax in public spaces. The prioritization of car transport by governmental and local authorities may result in discriminatory practices that infringe on children's right to access public services and contribute to the creation of an unsafe urban environment for children. The Netherlands cooperates with various groups to activate urban spaces and implement the UN CRC provisions. They involve children in the process of participation, creating cities with facilities for their needs and shaping social responsibility and citizenship among children and youth. By working together towards a common goal, based on mutual trust and competences, they are able to shape the activation of urban space in a way that benefits children and their well-being. The involvement of children in the planning process also helps to instill a sense of social responsibility and citizenship among them. This model of cooperation can serve as an inspiring example for other countries seeking to create more child-friendly cities through cross-sectoral collaboration. The panel aims to inspire and encourage decision-makers, urban planners, and community members to prioritize the needs and rights of children in the process of urban space design. By showcasing best practices from Poland and the Netherlands, we hope to demonstrate that child-friendly cities are not only a matter of ethics, but also an investment in the health, well-being, and future of our communities. We believe that by

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including children's voices and perspectives in the planning process, we can create more livable and equitable urban spaces for everyone.

Keywords

placemaking, participation, kids, city, urban playing

Short bios

Agnieszka Krzyżak-Pitura is a founder and CEO of the Polish NGO "Parent in the City" and an experienced activist working with local communities to create safer and more sustainable school streets. Her passion for inclusive and democratic cities has led her to collaborate with municipalities, government agencies, and other NGOs. She is dedicated to creating a participation process that includes children in placemaking and has authored several texts and publications on the topic. An expert in the Placemaking Europe Kids Working Group, speaker at the 10th Child in the City International Conference. In addition to her professional pursuits, she is also a music lover and a proud mother of three. Eager to share her insights and experiences with fellow conference attendees and engage in meaningful discussions on the future of urban development.

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Helena Szewiola is a graduate of the Faculty of Architecture at the Silesian University of Technology in Poland, where she is currently teaching urban planning. During her studies she attended and organized multiple workshops, lectures and extracurricular programs, gaining a complex insight into city planning. She also gained experience working in international offices like Wiencke Architekten, Medusa Group, Riegler Riewe Architekten and Studio Architektury. Former board member of ANTYRAMA Foundation, which focuses on changing cities through interdisciplinary ideas. Her focus lays on urban design, with a special interest in user inclusion. Currently she is working on her PhD thesis at the Doctoral School of the Silesian University of Technology. Her thesis focuses on the challenges, needs and methods of creating public spaces with special consideration of children.

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Beata Patużyńska has been involved for over 15 years in property sector as PR advisor. She is also a mother. Connecting the two roles she started investigating children's experience of a city. She believes that truly smart solutions are simple, and they don't need to employ state-of-the-art technology. Very often, children spot them first. She shares her findings via conferences presentations, writing and educating. She is based in Warsaw, Poland.

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Gooitske Zijlstra is an urban transformation specialist and the founder of gooitz. She collaborates with different companies and interdisciplinary collectives to create better public spaces that prioritize people's needs. Her fascination with human behavior in public spaces, and the reasons behind it, has led her to focus on the significance of places and the importance of involving all stakeholders, including children and those with disabilities, in the decision-making process. She is committed to creating child-friendly cities and has been actively sharing and developing tools to include children in complex decision-making processes.

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5. POSTERS

5.1.1. Eilidh Lamb: **Creating spaces for children to be seen and heard: Developing arts-based research methods for engagement with young people and their understandings of space in the new Bairns Hoose (Barnahus) in Scotland.**

A Barnahus model is comprised of a multi-agency team of professionals working together for children or young people who have witnessed or experienced violence. Barnahus' are places where multiple agencies work together in one premises for the benefit of children, young people, and families to promote safety, justice, and recovery from harm.

The Scottish Government have made a commitment to adapt and change the current systems and approaches for children, young people, and families to report instances of domestic and non-domestic violence, child maltreatment, child abuse, or neglect. The Scottish Barnahus model is being called the 'Bairns Hoose'.

The space, design, and functionality of the Bairns Hoose building are important not only for developing effective professional practices, but also in creating an environment which contributes to the recovery, safety and justice for child and youth victims and witnesses of violence.

This conceptual poster will discuss the development of inter-organisational relationships and building practitioner trust delivering when community-based workshops with children and young people. The poster notes the use of arts-based methods to explore how the perspectives of children and young people can support researchers and practitioners navigate multiple power relations when developing a new and innovative service in Scotland. Learning from children and young peoples' experiences and perceptions of space is critical for enriching children and young people's agency, power, autonomy, and participation.

Engaging with children and young people and using creative activities to express their views and perspectives on space is pivotal to developing environments which are child-centered and trauma-informed, the Scottish Bairns Hoose (and wider construction of Barnahus' models internationally).

This poster will explore the necessity of building trust which evolves with research and practice and offers reflections from community-based consultations on space with children and young people.

Keywords

barnahus, creative research, space, children, young people

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Short bio

Eilidh Lamb is a PhD. candidate in Social Work, School of Social and Political Science, University of Edinburgh, Scotland. She is an educator, academic, researcher and yoga teacher based in Scotland. Her practice interests are rooted in transformative pedagogies and working with young people. Her research interests include space, the design of spaces for trauma recovery, childhood studies, children's geographies, participation, and power.

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5.1.2. Marketa Michalcova & Tereza J. Brumovska: Youth's perceptions of support and empowerment from digital heroes and imaginary friends in daily experiences.

The proposed paper/poster will present the partial research results of the MSCA 10102791.project ENCOUNTER: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships, focus on youth's perceptions of the role of digital and imaginary heroes in their daily experiences. In project ENCOUNTER, while identifying and describing natural mentors and experiences with them in open-ended youth-centred questionnaires (n=533) and subsequent interviews (n=40) with school youth following the animated video on natural mentors; ten young people identified selected digital and imaginary heroes (influencers, actors, youtubers or fictional characters) as being significant for them in different aspects of their daily lives. Young people particularly identified Digital/Imaginary heroes in different roles as either primary natural mentors following the participatory task; or in the role of other identified supporters they described during interviews. Using the youth-centred perspective and the theoretical concepts of Digital empathy, para-friendships, empowerment, youth agency and social support, this paper will discuss: 1. The roles of Digital and Imaginary heroes in young people's daily lives in youth-centred perspective; 2. Similarity and differences in the roles and perceived benefits between Digital and Imaginary heroes and natural mentors in young people's perceptions. as their mentors. In this study, I am describing what is „a digital hero“ based on „digital empathy“ and „para-friendship“ concepts. I am discussing the questions: What are? How are the role and functions of the 'and in other perceived benefits of Digital heroes in comparison to natural mentors (according to the literature)

Keywords

digital heroes, youth-centred approach, digital empathy, para-friendship, youth's perspective, empowerment, youth agency

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Short bio

Marketa Michalcova is an MA student in Theoretical and Research Psychology @the Dept. of Psychology, Faculty of Humanities @Charles University and Science communication and research assistant in H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 project no. 101027291 ENCOUNTER: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships. She is also an active volunteer in youth mentoring social services organisation LATA. In her work, she is focusing on theories of social psychology, social sciences and has

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interest in research methods in child-and-youth-centred perspective with active inclusion of children & youth on their daily experiences with different social phenomena.

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5.1.3 Sara Filipiak & Beata Łubianka: Locus of control in adolescents with different levels of neuroticism.

Contemporary interdisciplinary studies on children's and adolescent's personality development indicate on the need of research on their autonomy, sense of agency and exerting control over surrounding reality. Early adolescence is one of the most important periods in the human lifecycle, because it abounds in numerous biological, cognitive and social changes which prepare a young man to face the challenges of adulthood. Increasing social demands lead to augmented number of stressors, therefore early adolescence is often a moment of temporal disruption in personality development and increased negative emotionality reflected in heightened neuroticism. This study aimed at analysis of differences in locus of control in early adolescents depending on the level of the neuroticism (low, medium, high). Both variables constitute an important factor in developing personality as both are a source of positive adaptation, satisfying relations with people, and general life satisfaction. There is a lack of contemporary analysis of their mutual relations among students at early stages of adolescence. The whole sample consisted of 286 Polish students ($M = 12.97$) attending to public elementary schools including 137 girls (48%) and 149 boys (52%). Locus of control was surveyed with the Locus of Control Questionnaire and neuroticism was measured with the Picture-Based Personality Survey for Children. The internal locus of control in both two types of situations: successes and failures, were highest in students with the lowest level of neuroticism. Differences between both types of LOC were observed between students with low and high levels of neuroticism and average and high levels. There were no differences between the low and average levels of neuroticism in both types of locus of control. The results are analysed in the context of the role of supporting proper personality development and mental health formation in adolescence.

Keywords

locus of control, neuroticism, adolescence, personality development

Short bio

Dr. Sara Filipiak is currently working as an Associate Professor at the Faculty of Education and Psychology, Department of Clinical Psychology and Neuropsychology, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University (UMCS), Lublin, Poland. She received her MA (2005-2009) and PhD (2015) in Psychology at UMCS. She specializes in child and adolescent developmental psychology, including development of personality and self-regulation.

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5.1.4 Beata Łubianka & Sara Filipiak: Youth perspectives for hope for success in a Polish sample.

This paper focuses on hope for success, which is a cognitive construct that is a source of motivation of actions and coping with different obstacles and difficult situations. It is possible due to assumption of own's power of will and abilities to use necessary competences and skills. A contemporary context of multiple economical, educational and labor market transformations cause sense of uncertainty and the necessity make risky decisions by adolescents. The analysis of the level of hope for success in adolescent boys and girls enables predicting how young people make decisions and think about their future in different spheres of life. From this reason, the aim of this study was to analyze hope for success in contemporary Polish adolescents who are at the onset of making future choices pertaining to educational paths and professional career. The sample consisted of 495 Polish students ($M = 15.54$) including 268 girls (54%) and 227 boys (46%) attending to public elementary schools. Hope for success was measured with Hope for Success Questionnaire. Results indicated that boys scored significantly higher in general Hope for success and in Power of will subscale. No differences between genders were found in Finding solutions subscale. Results were analyzed in the context of fostering personal resources of adolescents and promoting constructive strategies of stress coping and solving problems typical for adolescence.

Keywords

hope for success, power of will, adolescence, making decisions

Short bio

Beata Łubianka is currently working as an Associate Professor at the Faculty of Education and Psychology, Department of Psychology, Jan Kochanowski University, Kielce, Poland. She received her MA (1996-2001) and PhD (2011) in Psychology at The John Paul Catholic University of Lublin. She specializes in educational psychology, developmental psychology, psychology of individual differences.

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KEYNOTES PRESENTATIONS

Prof. Kay Tisdall

What can Childhood Studies add to Policy and Practice?

Dr. Lenka Vochocová

Spoiled weirdos and puppets of the Left? Cultural specifics of and intersectional perspectives to the discursive construction of youth civic activism in the Czech online media.

Prof. Marek Tesar

Theorizing Global Childhoods: Philosophies, Theories, and Practice.

Prof. Michal Molcho

Children's Studies – training the next generation of practitioners Michal Molcho.

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LIST OF PRESENTATIONS IN PARALLEL SESSION

Agnieszka Krzyżak-Pitura, Helena Szewiola, Beata Patuszynska & Gooitske Zijlstra

"Towards Child-Friendly Cities: The Importance of Inclusive Urban Space Design and its Impact on Children's Well-being".

Alexandra König, Jessica Schwittek & Katarzyna Jendrzey

The Child as an Agent in Transnational Families - Methodological and Theoretical Considerations Using the Example of a Polish-German Research Project.

Anezka Kuzmicova & Karolina Simkova

Children thinking about facts via nonfiction book design.

Ashley Woodfall

Who Do You Want to Be? Participatory Creative Method in a Study in to Children's Media and Aspirations.

Beata Łubianka & Sara Filipiak

Youth perspectives for hope for success in a Polish sample.

Beata Patuszynska

Empowering children through co-creation. Case study of writing a book with and for children about their first steps into urban independence.

Denisa Kollarova

Playground potentials: Tools of imagination.

Eleonora Teszenyi

Representing and interpreting children's voice through an arts-based platform.

Eilidh Lamb

Creating spaces for children to be seen and heard: Developing arts-based research methods for engagement with young people and their understandings of space in the new Bairns Hoose (Barnahus) in Scotland.

Grace Spencer & Jill Thomson

Problematizing empowerment: unpacking young African migrants' concepts of power and empowerment – implications for youth agency in the European context.

Helena Szewiola

Children in public space.

Jacob Kromdal, Sally Wiggins & Annerose Willemsen

Food for fantasy: Sharing imaginary worlds during preschool meals.

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John Potter & Michelle Cannon

Partnership and empowerment in research practice with children.

Karin Osvaldsson Cromdal, Jacob Kromdal & Daniel Persson-Thunqvist

Agency and ambiguity in young children's emergency calls.

Laura Migliorini, Martina Olcese & Paola Cardinali

Wellbeing, engagement with community settings and deprivation: A comparison between school-aged children with different ethnic backgrounds.

Leila Angod

Conceptualizing "voice" in school – based youth participatory action research: Constraints and new possibilities in anti-racism research.

Letizia Luini

Photo-production during research processes with children: free expression and participatory possibilities through photovoice.

Lydie Karnikova & Karolina Simkova

Young activists' perspectives on how society views their civic engagement in the online space.

Maria Manuel Vieira & Lia Pappámikail

Gaining access and cooperation: Some methodological challenges in research with adolescents.

Marketa Michalcova & Tereza J. Brumovska

Youth's perceptions of support and empowerment from digital heroes and imaginary friends in daily experiences.

Minkyung Kwon

Teenage girls navigating and challenging the contradictory construction of a 'girl-child': a theoretical contribution of 'childism'.

Molly Brooks

Urban livability and well-being: An evidence based approach to young peoples participation in research and creating change.

Natalie Canning

Acknowledging children's rights as a process to empowerment.

Natascia Micheli

Theological intelligence and learning in adolescents.

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Patricio Cuevas-Parra

Child-led research: Strengthening children's voice, empowerment and agency.

Pierangelo Barone, Camilla Barbanti, Veronica Berni & Monica Facciocchi

Speaking up through research, taking the floor in society: a participatory research study on the impact of the theatre laboratory at the "Cesare Beccaria" youth detention center in Milan.

Ruth Barnes

Exploring children's wellbeing and the concept of 'generagency' in sport: a youth sports case study.

Sara Filipiak & Beata Łubianka

Locus of control in adolescents with different levels of neuroticism.

Sándor Pálfi

Listening and hearing children's voices through rights based pedagogic practice.

Sheila Garrity, Monika Haid & Aidan Harte

Spaces and Traces Young children's meaning making through digital methodologies in a time of global pandemic.

Sonja Arndt, Kylie Smith & Nicola Yelland

Conceptualising 'the migrant child': Feminist, poststructural and posthuman speculations.

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MENTORING
Encounter

H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 Project no. 101027291 Encounter: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships
Faculty of Humanities, Charles University in Prague, the Czech Republic

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

PRE-CONFERENCE EVENING

from 19:00 Pre-conference informal social meet-up

VENUE: Náplavka Smíchov, Details TBC

CONFERENCE DAY 1

8:30-8:50 REGISTRATION, Coffee and Tea
8:50-9:00 Conference opening

9:00-10:15 KEYNOTE 1: Prof. Kay Tisdall
10:15-10:45 COFFEE BREAK
10:45-12:15 Parallel sessions 1

12:15-13:00 LIGHT LUNCH (Kavárna Hlína)
13:00-14:30 Parallel sessions 2

14:30-15:00 Coffee break
15:00-16:15 KEYNOTE 2: Prof. Marek Tesar
16:15-17:45 Parallel session 3

17:45-18:00 Day 1 Closure
18:00-19:30 (optional): TOUR AROUND PRAGUE WITH GUIDE
Meet-up outside the building A, Hybernská 4

from 19:30 CONFERENCE SOCIAL DINNER
(VENUE: Café & Restaurant Slavia,
Smetanovo nábřeží 1012/2, 110 00 Staré Město, Praha 1)

CONFERENCE DAY 2

8:00-8:55 REGISTRATION
9:00-9:15 Conference opening Day 2

9:15-10:30 KEYNOTE 3: Prof. Michal Molcho
10:30-10:45 COFFEE BREAK

10:45-12:00 KEYNOTE 4: Dr. Lenka Vochocova

12:00-12:30 LIGHT LUNCH (POSTERS PRESENTATION)

12:30-14:00 Parallel session 4

14:00-14:30 Conference closure

European
Commission

Horizon 2020
European Union funding
for Research & Innovation

PARALEL SESSIONS: PRESENTATIONS

PARALEL SESSION 1 (DAY 1; 10:45–12:15)

PS 1.1.

- 1.1.1. *John Potter & Michelle Cannon*: Partnership and empowerment in research practice with children
- 1.1.2. *Karin Osvaldsson Cromdal, Jacob Cromdal & Daniel Persson-Thunqvist*: Agency and ambiguity in young children's emergency calls
- 1.1.3. *Patricio Cuevas-Parra*: Child-led research: Strengthening children's voice, empowerment and agency

PS 1.2. SYMPOSIUM

- 1.2.1. *Sándor Pálfi*: Listening and hearing children's voices through rights based pedagogic practice
- 1.2.2. *Eleonora Teszenyi*: Representing and interpreting children's voice through an arts-based platform
- 1.2.3. *Natalie Canning*: Acknowledging children's rights as a process to empowerment

PS 1.3.

- 1.3.1. *Helena Szewiola*: Children in public space
- 1.3.2. *Denisa Kollarova*: Playground potentials: Tools of imagination
- 1.3.3. *Molly Brooks*: Urban livability and well-being: An evidence based approach to young peoples participation in research and creating change

PARALEL SESSIONS 2 (DAY 1; 13:00–14:30)

PS 2.1.

- 2.1.1. *Maria Manuel Vieira & Lia Pappámikail*: Gaining access and cooperation: Some methodological challenges in research with adolescents
- 2.1.2. *Letizia Luini*: Photo-production during research processes with children: free expression and participatory possibilities through photovoice
- 2.1.3. *Sheila Garrity, Monika Haid & Aidan Harte*: Spaces and Traces Young children's meaning making through digital methodologies in a time of global pandemic

PS 2.2.

- 2.2.1. *Pierangelo Barone, Camilla Barbanti, Veronica Berni & Monica Facciocchi*: Speaking up through research, taking the floor in society: a participatory research study on the impact of the theatre laboratory at the "Cesare Beccaria" youth detention center in Milan
- 2.2.2. *Ashley Woodfall*: Who Do You Want to Be? Participatory Creative Method in a Study in to Children's Media and Aspirations

PARALEL SESSIONS 3 (DAY 1; 16:15–17:45)

PS 3.1.

- 3.1.1. *Anezka Kuzmicova & Karolina Simkova*: Children thinking about facts via nonfiction book design
- 3.1.2. *Natascia Micheli*: Theological intelligence and learning in adolescents
- 3.1.3. *Lydie Kárníková & Karolína Šimková*: Young activists' perspectives on how society views their civic engagement in the online space

PS 3.2.

- 3.2.1. *Ruth Barnes*: Exploring children's wellbeing and the concept of 'generagency' in sport: a youth sports case study
- 3.2.2. *Sonja Arndt, Kylie Smith & Nicola Yelland*: Conceptualising 'the migrant child': Feminist, poststructural and posthuman speculations
- 3.2.3. *Leila Angod*: Conceptualizing "voice" in school - based youth participatory action research: Constraints and new possibilities in anti-racism research

PS 3.3. WORKSHOP

Agnieszka Krzyżak-Pitura, Helena Szewiola, Beata Patuszyńska & Gooitske Zijlstra: "Towards Child-Friendly Cities: The Importance of Inclusive Urban Space Design and its Impact on Children's Well-being"

PARALEL SESSIONS 4 (DAY 2; 12:30–14:00)

PS 4.1.

- 4.1.1. *Beata Patuszynska*: Empowering children through co-creation. Case study of writing a book with and for children about their first steps into urban independence
- 4.1.2. *Grace Spencer & Jill Thomson*: Problematizing empowerment: unpacking young African migrants' concepts of power and empowerment - implications for youth agency in the European context
- 4.1.3. *Jacob Cromdal, Sally Wiggins & Annerose Willemsen*: Food for fantasy: Sharing imaginary worlds during preschool meals

PS 4.2.

- 4.2.1. *Laura Migliorini, Martina Olcese & Paola Cardinali*: Wellbeing, engagement with community settings and deprivation: A comparison between school-aged children with different ethnic backgrounds
- 4.2.2. *Alexandra König, Jessica Schwittek & Katarzyna Jendrzey*: The Child as an Agent in Transnational Families - Methodological and Theoretical Considerations Using the Example of a Polish-German Research Project
- 4.2.3. *Kwon Minkyung*: Teenage girls navigating and challenging the contradictory construction of a 'girl-child': a theoretical contribution of 'childism'

POSTERS

- Sara Filipiak & Beata Łubianka*: Locus of control in adolescents with different levels of neuroticism
- Beata Łubianka & Sara Filipiak*: Youth perspectives for hope for success in a Polish sample
- Markéta Michalčová & Tereza J. Brumovská*: Youth's perceptions of support and empowerment from digital heroes and imaginary friends in daily experiences
- Eilidh Lamb*: Creating spaces for children to be seen and heard: Developing arts-based research methods for engagement with young people and their understandings of space in the new Bairns Hoose (Barnahus) in Scotland

CHILDREN AND YOUTH PERSPECTIVES CONFERENCE:
THEORY, RESEARCH AND PRACTICE IN EUROPEAN CONTEXT
PRAGUE 14TH – 15TH SEPTEMBER 2023

CALL FOR ABSTRACTS

A critique of the adult-centred theory and research methods traditionally used in the exploration of children and adolescent's development and lives entered the discourse of social sciences in the 1990s with the theory of New Sociology of Childhood (James and Prout, 1997), arguing that children and young people are in traditional discourses considered by adults as incompetent in their skills before developing into fully respectable adults. In terms of research, children and youth are traditionally treated as research subjects who provide the data in adult-centred categories on children's themes, resulting in information about children that is directed, analysed, and produced by adults in adult-centred views. In addition, the discussion of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child has ignited the discussion on the implementation of children's rights in children's daily encounters with social institutions, such as family, education and schools, social services, health services, law institutes etc.

The child-centred perspective aims to acknowledge, address and empower children's voice and active agency considering children as active social agents with their experiences and perspectives that are relevant to society. Yet, traditional discourses and related social policies on children and childhood still present barriers to child-centred perspective, inclusion, and active participation of children in democratic institutions and societies.

This recent development in social sciences is embedded in the new discipline of Childhood (Children's) studies with an interdisciplinary approach to the child, children, and childhood. With a child-centred focus, new research methods are friendly to children's mode of communication, allowing active participation in research and thus more authentic exploration of children's experiences and perspectives of the lived social phenomena in question.

To contribute to the current discussion on a child-centred perspective and further development of Childhood/Children's studies in the EU and the Czech context, we invite, academics, researchers, PhD. candidates, and practitioners to present the research and theoretical/conceptual papers, posters, symposium of the 3-5 papers, and reflections on child-centred evidence-based practice in social institutions, on the following topics:

1. The child-and-youth-centred approach, in theory, policy, research and applied evidence-based practice in the EU and the Czech context
2. Interdisciplinarity and latest development in child-centred perspective and discipline of Childhood/Children's studies
3. Concepts of child's agency, power, empowerment, autonomy, participation and children's voice in the theory of Childhood/Children's studies
4. UN CRC and Children's rights in theory, research, policy, current debate and evidence-based practice in the EU and the Czech context
5. Arts-based and participatory child-centred research methodologies and methods and application in exploration of children's experiences, perceptions, rights and child-centred evidence based evaluation and practice
6. Arts-based and participatory child-centred research with rural children, youth and young adults (up to 25 years) in EU context
7. Arts-based and participatory child-centred research with urban children, youth and young adults (up to 25 years) in EU context
8. Youth mentoring and the perspective of Childhood/Children's studies in the EU context

Register with conference ABSTRACTS (350 words) [HERE](#) until 31st March 2023

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

Book of abstracts will be generated and distributed to all conference participants. Selected abstracts and presentations will be called as conference proceedings for Special Issue on the conference themes, details TBC.

CONFERENCE FEES

Conference participant
Conference participant with presentation
PhD. students

130 Euro / 3000 CZK
150 Euro / 3500 CZK
100 Euro / 2500 CZK

Session fees: Please, email us with request for details.

CONTACT DETAILS

children.youth.perspectives.cuni.cz
children.youth.perspectives@fhs.cuni.cz
tereza.brumovska@fhs.cuni.cz

*This Children & Youth Perspectives Conference, Prague 2023 is part of a project ENCOUNTER: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101027291.

Children are considered here according to UN CRC as human beings between 0 – 18 years of age. Thus, the term 'children' includes children of 0 – 11 and young people in the age between 12 – 18 years in this conference synopsis. Young adults are people between 18 – 25 years of age also relevant for the conference call.

THEORY, RESEARCH AND PRACTICE IN EUROPEAN CONTEXT

PRAGUE 14TH - 15TH SEPTEMBER 2023

Venue: Campus Hybernska, Charles University, Hybernska 4, Prague 1, Czech Republic

Organisers: Charles University
Dept. of Psychology and Life Sciences, Faculty of Humanities
Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences
Institute of Czech Language and Theory of Communication, Faculty of Arts

H2020-MSCA-ST-IF-2020 Project no. 101027291 Encounter: Experiences of Youth in Natural Mentoring Relationships
Faculty of Humanities, Charles University in Prague, the Czech Republic

KEYNOTES

- **Prof. Michal Molcho** Dean of the School of Education and co-founder of Dept. of Children's Studies, University of Galway, Ireland
- **Prof. Kay Tisdall** Professor of Childhood Policy at the University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom
- **Prof. Marek Tesar** Head of the School of Learning Development and Professional Practice, Faculty of Education and Social Work, University of Auckland, Aotearoa/New Zealand
- **Dr. Lenka Vochocova** Lecturer and researcher in communication, media studies and youth, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University, Czech Republic

CONFERENCE THEMES

1. Child-centred theory, concepts and research methods
2. Children, UN CRC, social disadvantages, institutions and services
3. Children, play & imagination
4. Children & Space
5. Children & Media

[Registration for participants without conference paper here](#)

[Registration of conference fees payment here](#)

[More information about conference here](#)

Registration fees for participants without a presentation:

Day 1 and 2 (Including conference dinner)	80 Euro
Day 1 only	65 Euro
Day 2 only	50 Euro
Conference dinner	30 Euro

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CONFERENCE THEMES

The conference contributes to the current discussion and further development on a child-centred perspective in the field of Childhood/Children's studies in the EU and the Czech context. A critique of the adult-centred theory and research methods argues since 1990s that children and young people in traditional discourses are considered by adults as incompetent in their skills before developing into fully respectable adults. The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UN CRC) questions the implementation of children's rights in children's daily encounters with social institutions, such as family, education and schools, social services, health services, law institutes etc. The child-centred perspective aims to acknowledge, address and empower children's voice while considering children as active social agents with their experiences and perspectives that are relevant for society. In this perspective, the conference will discuss the following themes:

1. Child-centred theory, concepts and research methods
2. Children, UN CRC, social disadvantages, institutions and services
3. Children, play & imagination
4. Children & Space
5. Children & Media

More information:

Registration for participants
with no conference presentation
is open until 30th July 2023 here:

CHILDREN & YOUTH PERSPECTIVES CONFERENCE THEORY. RESEARCH AND PRACTICE IN EUROPEAN CONTEXT

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VENUE Campus Hybernska, Charles University, Hybernska 4,
Prague 1, Czech Republic

ORGANISERS Charles University Dept. of Psychology and Life Sciences,
Faculty of Humanities, Institute of Communication Studies
and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Institute of Czech
Language and Theory of Communication, Faculty of Arts

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Lecturer and researcher
in communication, media
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Faculty of Social
Sciences, Charles
University, Czech
Republic

CONFERENCE THEMES

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Special thanks to Ms. veronika Rocinova a Ms. Kristyna Gajova for their significant contribution in production of this conference publication.